

A Rural California CRNA Workforce Study

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Background

- In the US., there are 3 types of anesthesia providers: physician anesthesiologists (MDAs), certified registered nurse anesthetists (CRNAs), and anesthesiologist assistants.
- In CA, CRNAs and MDAs are sole anesthesia providers.
- CRNAs can practice independently in CA due to state opt-out status.
- Lack of California (CA) workforce study describing CRNA practice pattern

Aim

- Identify specific dimensions of CRNAs' practice in rural CA
- Describe professional issues faced by CRNAs in rural CA
- Describe impact of legislative changes among rural-practicing CRNAs within last 10 years
- Describe CRNAs' perspective on future supply and demand of anesthesia service in rural CA
- To publish results in AANA Journal

Review of Literature

- Shortages of anesthesia providers in rural areas and CRNAs are primary anesthesia providers in rural hospitals
- CRNAs-only models more cost-effective compared to other staffing models
- Uneven distribution of anesthesia providers in rural vs urban areas: CRNAs practice in counties with median income is less than 25th percentile, where patients were mostly uninsured, unemployed, and/or use Medicaid.

Method

- Design: descriptive, cross-sectional design
- Setting: In rural CA as defined by the Federal Office of Rural Health Policy (FORHP)
- Sample: A convenience sample of 34 CRNA respondents working in rural CA
- Collection Method: A survey sent to the CRNAs' electronic mails

Discussion

- All respondents from the nine counties in rural CA where CRNAs were sole providers:
 - Envisioned shortages of anesthesia providers with increasing demand at their facility within the next year
 - Indicated frequent on-call shifts, further correlating concurrent shortages of and continued demand of anesthesia providers within those areas

Results/ Findings

Practice Patterns of Rural CRNAs

- Overall response rate 6.8% from rural CRNAs
- The ethnicity of rural CRNAs are predominantly Caucasian, 40 to 50's age range, Master's degree prepared
- Majority of rural CRNAs have more than 20 years of experience with annual income mostly in the \$250,000-\$349,999 range.
- All primarily involved with direct patient care and working under independent 1099 practice without MDA available on staff.
- The majority of respondents reported to not have any call shifts, but second common response was one to three times per month
- 12 of 34 respondents reported to work at a critical access hospital
- 79% of rural CRNAs are willing to work in rural area in the next 5 years
- The majority of rural CRNAs do not plan to retire more than 10 years from now, but 8 of 34 respondents plan to retire within the next 5 years

Themes from Qualitative Questions

Primary issues faced by rural CRNAS

- Reimbursement inequity
- Competition with other contractors or anesthesiologists
- Poor work-life balance, having inadequate resource

Impact of legislative changes among rural-CRNAs

- AB5 limits practice, opt-out expands practice
- Need to make adjustments in business practice to work around politics

Future supply and demand of anesthesia services

- Current supply is inadequate - "continued to be short staffed"
- Foresee increase in demand - "the busiest and most booked I have been past 5 years"

Conceptual Frame Work - Iowa Model

Recommendation

- Both rural and urban-focused studies are needed to gain in-depth information that can help compare differences and allow the trending of practice patterns.
- Survey questions exploring the primary reasons for CRNAs working in rural CA may provide insights for strategizing recruitments and alleviating retentions
- Political measures and efforts should be employed to mitigate recent legislative changes and maintain the rural scope of practice
- CRNAs should be included in their institutional board decision-making to help make informed decisions and alleviate the sense of being taken over by anesthesiologists

Conclusion

- The number of doctorally prepared CRNAs will increase nationally within the next decade
- Professional advocacy in all aspects, whether it be education, politics, or actual clinical practice is needed within the CRNA profession
- With the perceived shortage of CRNAs and anticipated demands for anesthesia services in rural areas, more aggressive recruitment of CRNAs in rural California may be prudent